

estimated from Fig 1 are the following : (for 85% aq. HOAc)

Sodium chloride : 23 mhos cm^2 ; Sodium acetate : 18 mhos cm^2 ; Zinc chloride : 4 mhos cm^2 ; Zinc bromide : 4 mhos cm^2 .

The equivalent conductance at 25° and 0.1N concentration of sodium chloride in 85% aq. HOAc and in water⁷ are 14 and 111 mhos cm^2 , respectively. For sodium acetate, the corresponding values are 14 and 73 mhos cm^2 , respectively. From these values, we can conclude that for both sodium chloride and sodium acetate, the dissociation in 85% aq. HOAc is considerably lower than in water.

For zinc chloride, the equivalent conductance at 0.1N concentration in 85% aq. HOAc and in water⁷ are 1.6 and 82 mhos cm^2 , respectively. This shows that zinc chloride is dissociated only to a very small extent in 85% aq. HOAc compared to water. The behaviour of zinc bromide is likely to be similar to that of zinc chloride, because their equivalent conductances in 85% aq. HOAc are comparable (Fig. 1).

In 85% aq. HOAc, the equivalent conductance of bromine solutions (Table 2) is nearly equal to that of sodium chloride and sodium acetate (Table 1). This might be attributed to a slight hydrolysis of bromine in 85% aq. HOAc.

Conclusion

It may be of interest to point out here that the mechanism of the bromination of anisole^{2,8} in 85% aq. HOAc in the presence of added salts such as sodium and zinc salts, only undissociated molecular species of sodium chloride, zinc chloride, etc., are postulated as catalysts. The conductivity data for zinc chloride and zinc bromide discussed above offer support to this aspect of the mechanism of the bromination of anisole in the presence of zinc salts.

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Study on Montmorillonite from Santhal Parganas District in Bihar

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RAJMAHAL hills in Santhal Parganas district of Bihar extending between latitude 24°15' and 25 16' and longitude 87°18' and 87°46' running along river Ganga consist of a flow of basalt of Jurassic age and are said to be primitive mountain composed of black stone¹. Siddique and Bahl² and Satyabrat, Balu and Thomas³ have studied bentonite deposits in India which includes some information regarding the deposits in Bihar. Advancement in mineralogy has led to the academic interest in and economic importance of smectite clay minerals^{4, 5, 6}. We have been interested in our laboratories in the characterisation of the minerals of this area for a variety of reasons¹ and in this paper we are reporting the study of bentonite minerals in the district of Santhal Parganas.

Experimental

Bentonite samples from seven places as coded in Table 1 were taken for investigation. The samples were dried in an air oven for five hours and then powdered to pass through 150 mesh sieve (0.104 mm). The powder was dried in an air oven for 24 hours at 110-120°. The dried powder was cooled in a desiccator and used for all determinations^{2,3} and the properties are reported in Table 1.

All the samples under study were analysed qualitatively and quantitative estimations of some of the constituents were done (wherever feasible) without any pretreatment by standard procedures^{2,7}. The cation exchange capacity was determined by potassium carbonate method⁸ and also by ammonium acetate method⁹. The analytical data and C.E.C. values are recorded in Table 2.

X-ray powder diffractograms for some of the bentonite samples were recorded at the X-ray Laboratory of Indian Institute of Petroleum, Dehradun using X-ray unit X-RD-6 (General Electrical, U.S.A.) while those of the rest of the samples were recorded at the X-ray laboratory of Textile Technology Department of Indian Institute of Technology, New Delhi using Phillips Diffractometer.

I.R. spectra of all the samples were run as KBr pellets on Hilger Watts H 800 i.r. spectrophotometer¹ in the region 400-700 cm^{-1} . The observed i.r. frequencies and X-ray data are reported in Table 3 and Table 4 respectively.

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TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Sample No.	Code No.*	Colour	Swelling power	Gel Volume	% Loss on ignition	pH	Stain**	Sp. gr.
1.	SRHB-1	Grey	2.7	6	4.53	7.60	+	2.27
2.	SRHB-3	Brown	2.1	5	—	7.25	+	2.05
3.	SRHB-8	Brown	1.5	4	11.61	8.25	—	—
4.	SRHB-12	Grey	2.0	5	—	8.30	+	2.35
5.	SRHB-13	Grey	2.8	7	8.51	6.25	+	2.23
6.	SRHB-14	Grey	2.2	5	3.07	7.10	+	2.24
7.	SRHB-22	Grey	2.1	7	14.63	8.65	+	—

* SRHB-1-Bakudih, SRHB-3-Mandali, SRHB-8-Simaljuri, SRHB-12-Kusmafatak, SRHB-13-Madhiyo Badi Pahar, SRHB-14-Balbnadari, SRHB-22-Sihli

** Stain Test+mean Benzidine Test Positive.

TABLE 2—CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND CATION EXCHANGE CAPACITY

Sample No.	Al ₂ O ₃ %	Fe ₂ O ₃ %	TiO ₂ %	P ₂ O ₅ %	H ₂ O % (110°)	MnO ₂ %	CEC K ₂ CO ₃ me/100 g	CEC NH ₄ Ac me/100 g
1.	26.82	2.07	1.00	Tr	10.83	Neg	72.00	75.00
2.	33.06	9.32	1.30	Tr	15.49	0.20	96.00	97.50
3.	23.76	7.49	—	0.10	0.60	0.10	9.60	16.30
4.	23.04	6.49	1.50	Tr	17.85	0.20	33.60	35.70
5.	19.18	—	1.40	Tr	12.55	0.10	86.40	—
6.	31.82	7.66	1.00	Tr	11.30	0.50	52.40	54.00
7.	—	4.33	2.40	Tr	2.50	—	64.80	66.00

Tr = Traces.

TABLE 3—INFRARED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES

SRHB-1	SRHB-3	SRHB-8	SRHB-12	SRHB-13	SRHB-22
cm ⁻¹					
3675	—	3680	3680	—	3640
3400	3440	—	3460	3440	1650
1640	1640	1640	1650	1650	3460
1080	1030	1030	1000	1040	1030
			1050	—	
915	915	915	915	915	915
—	—	750	790	765	750
			750		

Results and Discussion

Similarity in the values of C.E.C. by ammonium acetate and potassium carbonate methods (Table 2) indicates that for all but one samples (simaljuri) the exchangeable cations are bivalent, e.g., calcium and

magnesium. No other bivalent cation has been reported to occur in the exchangeable state. In regard to the cation exchange property these samples are superior to the samples of Rajasthan where the variation is reported to be 11 to 54 m.e. per 100 g. sample². It is relevant to note that more than 60 per cent of Rajasthan bentonites are reported to occur as exchangeable sodium, that is, these contain predominantly monovalent cations in exchangeable state.

The swelling power of these samples are relatively low (on an average two times *vide* Table 1) as compared to those of Rajasthan samples which swell three to five times². The gel volume varies from 4 to 7 ml as against those of Rajasthan samples where the variation is reported to be 2 to 20 ml though the most common value is 5 ml². The

TABLE 4—X-RAY POWDER DATA (d VALUES*)

SRHB-3 A°	SRHB-8 A°	SRHB-12 A°	SRHB-13 A°	SRHB-14 A°	SRHB-22 A°	Reported Data	
						Montmorillonite A°	Kaolinite A°
4.3533	4.5521	6.5589	4.4938	4.5764	5.0676	4.5000	7.1500
2.8400	4.3923	4.2300	3.5900	4.2909	3.5900	2.6000	4.4800
2.4947	3.6627	4.0042	2.5287	3.7547	3.0481	2.2500	4.3920
15.5044	2.5996	3.4662	15.7810	3.1318	15.2973	1.7060	4.1720
	2.3324	3.2434		2.2813		1.5030	3.7360
		2.4947		2.7467		1.9010	3.5730
		2.2813		15.5044		1.2520	3.1480
							3.0980
							2.7480
							2.5660
							2.4830
							2.3850
							2.8800

* See text.

pH values are consistent with the fact that Rajmahal volcanics are predominantly basic.

The observed i.r. and X-ray data have been tabulated in Tables 3 and 4 and a comparison of the observed data with reported values confirm the presence of Montmorillonite clay mineral in all the samples along with Kaolinite in minor proportions.

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Studies in the Synthesis of Anticancer Agents : Part IV. Nitrogen Mustards of 9-Phenanthroyl Chlorides

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It is generally considered that the nitrogen mustards owe their antitumour activity to their ability to cyclise to the highly reactive ethylenimonium ions(I) in polar solvents such as water¹. This cyclisation cannot occur if a proton is coordinated with the nitrogen atom. Hence, nitrogen mustards are relatively stable in dilute aqueous solutions and at the physiological pH². The resulting ethylenimonium ions or in the case of ethylenimines or epoxides, the polarisable three membered rings react with compounds containing a readily replaceable hydrogen atom such as in the free amino group of nucleic acids etc. The weakly basic aromatic

nitrogen mustards may react with nucleophilic biological systems by way of a carbonium ion intermediate, since their cyclic ethylenimonium forms are relatively unstable, probably by a cross linking mechanism.

In continuation of our work on studies in the synthesis of nitrogen mustards as anticancer agents³⁻⁵ we report in this paper the synthesis of nitrogen mustards from 9-phenanthroyl chloride⁶ and 2,3,6-trimethoxy-9-phenanthroyl chloride and also their anticancer activity.

9-Phenanthroyl chloride(II) on condensation with N, N-bis(2-chloroethyl)amine⁷ afforded phenanthrene-9-[N,N-bis(2-chloroethylenimonium)] carboxamide ion(III). I.R. spectrum of (III) showed a strong band at 1722 cm⁻¹ supporting the ethylenimonium structure. 2,3,6-Trimethoxy-9-phenanthroyl chloride (IIa) on similar condensation with N,N-bis(2-chloroethyl)amine gave [N,N-bis(2-chloroethyl)-2,3,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene-9-carboxamide(IV) which showed a band at 1647 cm⁻¹ in its i.r. spectrum. This on further crystallisation from aqueous ethanol rearranged to 2,3,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene-9-[N,N-bis(2-chloroethylenimonium)] carboxamide ion(IIIa), which showed a strong band at 1700 cm⁻¹ indicating that rearrangement has taken place during crystallisation from aqueous ethanol.

(II) R = R₁ = R₂ = H

(IIa) R = R₁ = R₂ = OCH₃